

MULTICONDUCTOR CABLE COUPLING PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study of the response of shielded multiconductor cables to external fields. Of primary interest is the dependence of the internal wire response on the geometry or complexity of the cable. Long lengths (up to 150m) of the cables were tested using the HDL CW Instrumentation System (CWIS) [1]. A review of multiconductor transmission line theory for shielded cables is provided and the experimental results analyzed.

Introduction

This paper presents experimental results obtained on a set of simple multiconductor cables with external electromagnetic shields. The purpose of the experiment was to investigate the relationship between the internal cable geometry and the electromagnetic pulse (EMP) coupling to the cables. A set of five cables, shown in Figure 1, were selected for this investigation. The cables have an increasing number of internal conductors, from 3 to a maximum of 8, and similar construction and external shielding. A physical and electrical description of the tested cables is provided, followed by details of the experiment conducted. The experiment was performed on relatively long (30 to 150m) lengths of cable using a radiating electromagnetic source. A summary of multiconductor transmission line theory is then given prior to an analysis of the results from the experiment.

Cable Descriptions

Measurements were performed to obtain the EMP response of the five different multiconductor cable geometries depicted in Figure 1. The multiconductor

cables used in these measurements were selected from a group in the Alpha Wire Company 1712 series.

This series was selected because of the conductor size, the range of the number of conductors, the type of insulation used and the construction of the overall braided shield. The internal wires are all number 20 AWG stranded tinned copper with a polyethylene insulation. The overall shield for each cable is made of braided tinned copper wires.

The physical parameters of each cable shield were determined from laboratory measurements and manufacturer's data. Six parameters were recorded to characterize the shield of each cable: the angle of the braid (α), the radius of the shield (a), the number of belts of wire (C), the number of belt crossings per unit length (P), the number of wires per belt (N) and the wire diameter (d). The resistance, transfer inductance and transfer capacitance of the shield were computed from these parameters using the work of Vance [2].

Figure 2 lists the cable shield specifications and the calculated coupling characteristics. The dc resistances of the cable shields and the internal wires were measured using a Biddle micro-ohm meter. The measured shield resistance and the average wire resistance are also given for each cable in Figure 2.

The conductor to conductor positions relative to each other were found to remain constant over the length of the cables. The absolute position of a conductor inside the shield varied with the lay of each cable.

Figure 1: Multiconductor Cable Cross Sections

Conductor Parameter		SHIELD PARAMETERS										
Cable Type	No. of Cond	Cond Res. mΩ/m	Alpha	Radius	Belts	Picks	Wires Per Belt	Wire Diameter	Resistance		Transfer Inductance	Coupling Capacitance
			α Degrees	(a) cm	(C)	(P)	(N)	(d) cm	Calculated mΩ/m	Measured mΩ/m	nH/m	nF/m
1713	3	33.9	21.2	0.183	14	6	7	0.013	14.2	12.9	1.79	42.5
1715	4	35.7	26.9	0.205	16	8	6	0.016	10.0	10.5	.896	96.0
1716	5	34.5	24.5	0.230	15	6	8	0.013	11.9	11.5	1.78	46.8
1717	6	34.0	32.3	0.256	16	8	7	0.016	9.05	9.42	1.00	96.3
1719	8	37.7	34.9	0.282	16	8	7	0.016	9.33	9.80	1.48	67.2

Figure 2: Cable Characteristics

EXPERIMENT

The experiment consisted of a set of measurements on relatively long lengths of each cable type shown in Figure 1. The lengths of the tested cables are provided in Figure 3.

Number of Conductors	Length in meters
3	151.8
4	151.2
5	148.5
3	30.5
6	29.7
8	31.7

Figure 3: Cable Samples Tested

Measurements were made of the electromagnetic fields illuminating the cables. The measurements performed on each cable consisted of external shield currents and internal voltages and currents. Open circuit voltage measurements were made between each conductor and ground (wire open circuit voltage) of each cable and between each cable bundle of conductors connected together and ground (bulk open circuit voltage), current measurements were made on each cable conductor and for the bundle of all inner conductors with all wires terminated in a short circuit.

The short circuit current measurements on internal wires were performed using a Tektronix CT-1 current probe as shown in Figure 4. All voltage measurements were obtained with a Tektronix P6046 differential voltage probe, Figure 5. The cable shield currents, see Figure 6, and bulk short circuit currents were measured with an EATON 91550-1 current probe. The reference measurement was taken with a half-turn magnetic field sensor. The electric field measurements were performed with a capacitive plate electric field sensor.

Test Configurations

The test layout is shown schematically in Figure 7. Measurements were performed on each cable with the cable suspended at a height of 2 meters and on the ground. The cables were set parallel to and 50 meters from the CWIS antenna with the center of the cable aligned with the center of the antenna. The cables were terminated at each end with shielded instrumentation boxes, see Figure 6. The shields of the cables were terminated at the box with flanged tubular adapters and the internal conductors were brought into the box through the adapters. Each instrumentation box was positioned on the ground and grounded to earth with three electrodes, each 5 feet in length.

The cable shield current measurements were performed with all equipment outside the instrumentation boxes. All short circuit current measurements were taken with the current probe and the fiber optic transmitter inside one of the shielded instrumentation boxes. The fiber optic cables exited the box through waveguide beyond cutoff ports. The instrumentation boxes were used as a ground point during the short circuit current measurements and all voltage measurements were made with respect to the same ground point.

The open circuit voltage measurements were made with all of the cable conductors unterminated at each end. The battery and inverter used to power the differential voltage probe were also contained in the shielded enclosure for these measurements.

The component of the electric field parallel to the axes of the cables and the CWIS antenna, was measured at locations corresponding to the center and each end of the cables at a height of 2 meters. These measurements were taken to characterize the field existing along the cable.

Reference Sensor & Re-referencing

All measurements were taken relative to an external reference. The reference chosen at the time

Figure 4: Measurement of Short Circuit Current

Figure 5: Measurement of Open Circuit Voltage

Figure 6: Measurement of Current on the Cable Shield

Figure 7: Cable Experimental Layout

of the test was the major component of magnetic field at a distance of 15 meters from the antenna structure. Following testing, all data were re-referenced to either the electric field or the shield current measurement of the cable under test at the appropriate measurement height. This was accomplished by dividing the measurement referenced to the magnetic field by the new reference transfer function, which was also referenced to magnetic field. All internal cable data presented in this paper are relative to the shield current measurement.

Theoretical Review

The response of a multiconductor transmission line due to distributed electromagnetic excitation has been studied by many researchers [3,4]. A convenient and compact solution for the terminal response of a multiconductor line is provided by Paul [5]. The work of Paul may be applied to a shielded multiconductor cable, represented in Figure 8, providing the source terms, \bar{V}_s and \bar{I}_s , are properly defined.

Figure 8: Shielded Multiconductor Cable Sources

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The terminal response of the cable in Figure 8 is given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}(l) \\ \bar{I}(l) \end{bmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{O}}(l) \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}(0) \\ \bar{I}(0) \end{bmatrix} + \int_0^l \bar{\mathcal{O}}(l-\xi) \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_s(\xi) \\ \bar{I}_s(\xi) \end{bmatrix} d\xi \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{\mathcal{O}}(l) = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}^{-1} \bar{T} \cosh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l) \bar{T}^{-1} \bar{C} & -\bar{Z}_c \bar{T} \sinh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l) \bar{T}^{-1} \\ -\bar{T} \sinh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l) \bar{T}^{-1} \bar{Z}_c^{-1} & \bar{T} \cosh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l) \bar{T}^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{Z}_c = \bar{C}^{-1} \bar{T} \bar{\gamma} \bar{T}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\gamma} = \bar{T}^{-1} [\bar{C} \bar{L}]^{1/2} \bar{T} \quad (4)$$

and \bar{T} is a similarity transformation such that $\bar{\gamma}$ is an $n \times n$ positive definite diagonal matrix and \bar{L} and \bar{C} are the line inductance and capacitance matrices. The voltage source vector, \bar{V}_s , is given approximately by [6]:

$$\bar{V}_s(\xi) = -Z_1 I_e(\xi) \bar{1} \quad (5)$$

where Z_1 is the transfer impedance of the cable shield, I_e is the external shield current at location ξ and $\bar{1}$ is a unity vector. The current source vector is given as [7]:

$$\bar{I}_s(\xi) = -j\omega \bar{C} \bar{V}_s'(\xi) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{C} is the line capacitance matrix, ω is the radian frequency and \bar{V}_s' is the potential at each wire due to the fields external to the cable. The coupling capacitance to the i^{th} wire is defined as:

$$c_i = Q_e(\xi) / V_{si}'(\xi) \quad (7)$$

where Q_e is the charge on the external cable shield and V_{si}' is the i^{th} element of \bar{V}_s' . Noting that the charge, Q_e , is given by:

$$Q_e(\xi) = C_e V_e(\xi) \quad (8)$$

where C_e is the capacitance of the cable over ground, the required current source, I_s , in equation (1) is found to be:

$$\bar{I}_s(\xi) = -j\omega \bar{C} \left[1/c_1 \dots 1/c_N \right]^T C_e V_e(\xi) \quad (9)$$

The individual wire coupling capacitances, c_i , and the

total shield coupling capacitance, C_s , are related by:

$$C_s = \sum_{i=1}^N [c_i] \quad (10)$$

The nature of the distribution of the c_i is under investigation.

Therefore the voltage source, \bar{V}_s , depends on the external shield current and the current source, \bar{I}_s , is a function of the external shield to ground voltage. If the tested cables were subjected to an ideal, horizontally polarized plane wave with the electric field, E_x , parallel to the cable, the external current excited on the cable shield would be constant over the length of the cable and given by:

$$I_e(x) = E_x / (\Gamma Z_0) \quad (11)$$

where Γ is the external cable propagation constant and Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of the cable over the ground. Equation (11) also requires that the terminations to the earth are perfect. The short circuit terminations at the ends of the cable to earth cause the external voltage, V_e , to be zero over the length of the cable:

$$V_e(x) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Both equations (11) and (12) were obtained using the work of Schelkunoff [8]. The actual experimental conditions will not be perfect due to the non-planar waves produced by the simulator [1] and the finite impedances of the terminations with the earth. However, the external current and voltage distributions given in equations (11) and (12) indicate that transfer impedance coupling, equation (5), will dominate the internal wire response.

Of interest here is the open circuit voltage and short circuit current for the internal wires of the shielded multiconductor cable due to the external current and voltage defined in equations (11) and (12). Substituting equations (3), (9), (11) and (12) into equation (1) and solving for the open circuit voltages ($\bar{I}(0)=\bar{I}(l)=0$) yields:

$$\bar{V}_{oc}(0) = -\bar{V}_{oc}(l) = \bar{Z}_c \bar{T} \bar{\Psi} \bar{T}^{-1} \bar{Z}_c^{-1} \bar{V}_s \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{\cosh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}_i l)}{j\omega\bar{\gamma}_i \sinh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}_i)} & , \quad i=j \\ 0 & , \quad i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

If the cable is homogeneous, all of the propagation modes are equal and equation (13) reduces to:

$$\bar{V}_{oc}(0) = -\bar{V}_{oc}(l) = \frac{(\cosh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l) - 1)}{j\omega\bar{\gamma} \sinh(j\omega\bar{\gamma}l)} \bar{V}_s \quad (15)$$

A similar result is obtained for the short circuit current response of the cable:

$$\bar{I}_{sc}(0) = \bar{I}_{sc}(l) = \bar{T}^{-1} \bar{\gamma}^{-1} \bar{T}^{-1} \bar{Z}_c^{-1} \bar{V}_s / (j\omega) \quad (16)$$

or for the case of a homogeneous cable:

$$\bar{I}_{sc}(0) = \bar{I}_{sc}(l) = \bar{Z}_c^{-1} \bar{V}_s / (j\omega\gamma) \quad (17)$$

The equations presented above will be used in the following analysis section.

Analysis of Results

The cable shield current was measured at three locations for each cable and height. Figure 9 shows a comparison of the three measurements for the 3 conductor 152 meter cable at ground height. The three shield current measurements have been re-referenced to the electric field at the center and parallel to the cable. As indicated by equation (11), the normalized current should decrease linearly with frequency. The shield currents are seen to parallel the 1/f line drawn in Figure 9 over the range of 100 kHz to 10 MHz. Ideally, the current should be identical at all three locations. The shield current is dependent on the electric field such that changes in the electric field from one location to another affects the current on the cable shield. The fact that the three measurements are very similar indicates that equations (11) and (12) are reasonably accurate for the experiment.

Figure 9: Normalized Shield Current at the Ends (Dashed +75, Dotted -75) and Center (Solid) of a Long Cable on the Ground

Open circuit voltage measurements from each wire to the shield within the same cable were found to be similar for the majority of the cables. This is shown in Figure 10 for the open circuit voltage measurements on two wires and the bundle of all wires connected together of the 4 conductor cable at ground height. The same result was obtained at a height of 2m. This

finding is consistent with equations (15) and (5) that predict equal open circuit voltages for each wire of a shielded homogenous cable excited only by the shielded transfer impedance.

The exception to the nearly equal voltage distribution was the three conductor cable where the voltage was from 5 to 10 dB different from one wire to another as shown in Figure 11. Both the long and short cables exhibited differences in the voltages over at least a portion of the frequency spectrum. Physical examination of the inner cable construction did not identify a potential source of the differences, nor did the dc resistances vary for the wires.

Figure 10: Open Circuit Voltage Comparison for Single Wires and the Bundle of the Four Conductor Cables

Figure 11: Open Circuit Voltages for the Short 3 Conductor Cable

Examination of the cable shield indicated that it was fairly open (low optical coverage) and this condition could mean that the approximation in equation (5) is incorrect. However, the five conductor cable had a similar looseness in the cable shield but the voltages for each wire were found to be equal. At present, the only explanation for the different wire responses is the fact that the three conductor cable has multiple modes of propagation (propagation velocity). As identified by equations (13) and (14) and as discussed in [7], a non-homogenous cable can have differences in the open circuit voltages. Evidence of

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multiple modes on the three conductor cable is seen in Figure 11 where each wire voltage peaks at a slightly different frequency (from 3 to 3.3 MHz).

The open circuit voltages for a single wire in each of the three long cables are presented in Figure 12. The low frequency responses of the cables are not exactly as expected from the measured dc resistances given in Figure 2 but are within the ± 2 dB accuracy of the CWIS. At the high frequencies (>1 MHz) where the shield inductance will dominate the coupling, the 4 conductor cable is about 15 to 20 dB lower than the 3 and 5 conductor cables. This difference is attributed to a difference in the shield inductance for the 4 conductor cable. Preliminary measurements of shield transfer inductance showed that the 3 conductor cables inductance is about 17 dB greater than the 4 conductor cable.

Figure 12: Open Circuit Voltages for 3 (Solid), 4 (Dashed) and 5 (Dotted) Conductor Cables

At the time of the test, the six and eight conductor cables were not available in lengths of 152 meters. In order to substantiate comparisons from one cable to another, both 31 and 152 meter lengths of the three conductor cable were tested to study the effects of cable length on the measurements of interest. Figure 13 shows a comparison of the bundle voltage measurements of the 31 and 152 meter lengths of the three conductor cable at ground height. A 20dB offset has been added to the short cable to aid in clarifying the two measurements.

The long cable resonates at a lower frequency than the short cable. The peaks in the open circuit voltage measurement occur where $f = 1/(2\gamma l)$ with l being the length of the cable and γ being the propagation mode from equation (15). The resonance of the short cable (f_s) can be computed from the resonance of the long cable (f_l) from $f_l = f_s l_s / l_l$, where l_l and l_s are the lengths of the long and short cables respectively. Using the values from the measured data it is found that if the short cable resonates at 3 MHz the long cable is expected to resonate at approximately 603 kHz, as shown in the figure.

At low frequencies, the voltage measurements are largely dependent on the total dc resistance of the shield. Because the resistance per unit length is

approximately the same for the long and short three conductor cables, the difference between the voltage measurements of the long and short cables is dependent on length and equal to $20 \cdot \log_{10}(l/l_s)$. For the tested lengths, this should be approximately 14 dB. The measured difference (accounting for the 20 dB offset) is about 12 dB at the low frequencies.

Figure 13: Bundle Voltage of Short (Solid) and Long (Dashed) 3 Conductor Cables

Similar to Figure 12, the open circuit voltages for a single wire of each of the short cables are displayed in Figure 14. Again the 3 conductor cable exhibits a response at low frequencies that is slightly larger than expected. The 6 conductor cable shows a lower response than the other cables at the high frequencies. The calculated transfer inductance for the 6 conductor cable is lower than the others and therefore, is believed to cause the lower response.

Variation in short circuit current measurements from one wire to another within the same cable were noticed in only the 3 and 8 conductor cables. The same type of differences found in the voltage measurements were found in the current measurements in the three conductor cable in that the measurements were close at low frequencies and diverged at the frequencies corresponding to a resonance frequency of the cable.

Figure 14: Open Circuit Voltages for 3 (Solid), 6 (Dashed) and 8 (Dotted) Conductor Cables

The open circuit voltages for the 8 conductor cable were all essentially equal. All current measurements were approximately the same for the 8 conductor cable except for the current on the black wire. As shown in Figure 1, all the cables except the eight conductor cable are constructed with all internal wires symmetrically organized around the inner edge of the shield. However, the black wire of the 8 conductor cable was located in the center with all other wires oriented symmetrically around it. Consequently, the impedance of the center wire is higher, resulting in a lower current measurement on the black wire than any other wire. Figure 15 compares current measurements for several of the wires in the 8 conductor cable including the black wire in the center of the cable. The currents converge at the low frequencies due to the fact that the dc resistances of the wires are the same. At the high frequencies, the impedance of the wire connections to the shield begin to dominate the current response and the currents on all of the wires again converge.

Figure 15: Short Circuit Currents for the Red, Black (Dashed), Green, Yellow and White Conductors of the 8 Conductor Cable

As identified in equation (17) the short circuit current is dependent on the inverse of the impedance matrix, \bar{Z}_c . It is also noted that the cable resonances, present at 3 MHz for the short cable open circuit voltages, are not completely absent in the short circuit current in Figure 15 as equation (17) would predict. However, the resonances are not nearly as strong and the $1/f$ dependence is seen at low frequencies where Z_T is mostly resistive. The flattening of the current response at high frequencies (where $f > 5$ MHz) is due to the shield inductance dominating the response.

Conclusion

A series of measurements were made on a set of multiconductor cables in order to study the effects of the internal cable geometry on the EMP response of the cables. The results indicate that the most complex effect on the coupling occurred in the simplest cable, a 3 conductor cable. The differences noted in the wire response were as great as 14 dB for the 3 conductor cable while the differences for the other cables were less than the measurement accuracy. The wide variance in the 3 conductor cable response is attributed to the existence of multiple TEM propagation modes in

the cable. The cables with more conductors did not appear to support more than one TEM mode of propagation.

The cable to cable response comparisons indicated that any differences noted were due to the external shield construction differences and not due to the internal cable geometry. The measured responses appeared to be in good general agreement with multiconductor transmission line theory.

The response of the more complex cables (with multiple layers of internal conductors) was found to be dependent on the impedance matrix, \bar{Z}_c , under load conditions where \bar{Z}_c is large. Otherwise, the geometry of the cable did not seem to effect the response. It should be pointed out that this conclusion is based on a limited set of cables and conditions that tended to maximize the internal response dependence on the shield transfer impedance, Z_T . Future efforts will focus on the effects of cable geometry on the capacitive coupling term for the cable shield.

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